

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Juan Kasal App: Web based application for event planning and cost estimation with linear regression

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to discuss the services. That will provide quality in event management processes. Our goal is to not only provide quality, but also to make it affordable and customized for the clients. Primary and secondary data were gathered for the study. Data sources (observations, internet resources, press and other sources. The proposed system intends to use Android application for effectively managing all stages of an event management procedure and give the user the ability to customize the event's quality based on his or her preferences needs. The application of project management to the creation and development of large or small events is known as event management. Festivals, conferences, ceremonies, formal parties, concerts, and conventions are examples of large-scale events. Given the current situation we are developing an Android application for event management to address system issues. The application will only be available to Android users.

The application will primarily cover educational, medical, and social events. The app will be built with Android Studio, and the back end will be managed in a SQL database. The application will be have easy and feasible GUI for all type of users. The event management industry has expanded rapidly in recent years industry (3rd). We present an Android mobile phone application in this paper to make it easier for a layman to plan an event in a hassle-free manner. This application will assist him/her in planning a successful and fun event. The system allow users to register on the application for an event. This proposed to be a web application. The project provides most of the basic functionality required for an event type e.g. [marriage, Dance Show birthday party, etc.], the system then allows the user to select date and time of event, place and the event equipment. All the data is logged in the database and the user is given a receipt number for his booking. The data is then send to administrator (website owner) and they may interact with the client as per his requirement.

Keywords: Web-Based Application; Event-planning; Cost-estimation; Linear-Regression

1. Introduction

Web Based Application for Event Planning and Cost Estimation is a system or an application that operates a segment in the entertainment, catering, designs and management sectors. It accepts bids from clients to arrange events in addition to providing musicians for entertainment purposes; artists and stylists for hair and make-up, cater management for food, flower owners for flower arrangement, this requires project management all in all. Sadly, the majority of events and it's project management tasks are still completed by hand, making them susceptible to a variety of problems and human error, including document loss, inaccurate project cost calculations, and miscommunication among project staff. Some struggles of clients are responsibility and job to deal with the event coordinators. News with the issue between the coordinators are spreading in social media, examples were the coordinators committed theft with the trusted budgets of clients. These weaknesses compelled us to create a project management tool in order to meet their

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requirements. As a result, we the author made an effort to create an integrated, user-friendly project management program with all the necessary project management elements that the system required.

Innovation in technology has improved human welfare. Indeed, advances in technology over the past 70 years have allowed people to live relatively happily in society. These are a few of the more noteworthy benefits. Although design systems have been around for a while, businesses are becoming more interested in them as a means of keeping their customers' experiences consistent across an expanding range of digital goods, websites, applications, and gadgets. A design system is an assembly of reusable parts with usage guidelines that are well-defined. Because it makes tasks more efficient, modern technology increases productivity by enabling humans to complete tasks in less time. Meanwhile, human error can be decreased and better decisions can be made because of the abundance of information available. One of the most difficult challenges for planners is balancing expenses and revenue sources in order to meet your organization's financial objectives. A budget is a detailed financial forecast for your event. It assists you in managing your spending and expectations by outlining exactly what you're spending (including fixed and variable costs), your projected revenue, and how much revenue you need to earn to meet your goals. This is true whether you're creating a budget for a corporate event, a trade show, or a conference.

Virtual event management software is comprehensive intended to streamline the entire event management process, from event registration and ticketing to attendee engagement and post-event analytics solution that enables event organizers to easily and efficiently plan, execute, and monitor virtual events. It includes a plethora of features and functionalities. Furthermore, virtual event management software boosts attendee engagement and interaction. It includes interactive features such as live chat, Q&A sessions, exhibitor booths, and opportunities, allowing participants to make meaningful connections. You get analytics and reporting capabilities with event management software. Organizers can collect valuable data on attendee behavior, session popularity, and levels of engagement, allowing them to measure event success, identify areas for improvement, and make data-driven decisions for future events.

Mobile applications are the best part that has come into use and has been continuously improved since the introduction of smartphones. Apps are like interesting and creative decorations that define the best uses of mobile phones. These make the use of technology feasible and understandable. Developers strive to create the most convenient functionalities in mobile apps that humans can use to simplify and entertain their tasks. Mobile apps are typically designed for information retrieval and productivity. Because of the availability of various tools and technology, people have begun to focus on other morals and purposes, which has expanded the category list. Furthermore, the increased capabilities of smartphones result in flawless app design and usage.

1.1. Statement of the problem

Problem #1: One problem with manual events planning is that it can be difficult to keep track of all the details and tasks involved in planning a events. With multiple vendors to coordinate, guest lists to manage, and deadlines to meet, couples may struggle to stay organized and avoid missing important details.

Problem #2: Another problem is that manual events planning can be costly, particularly if clients opt to hire a professional event planner. Events planners can charge significant fees for their services, which may not be feasible for customers with limited budgets.

Problem #3: Finally, manual events planning can be time-consuming, particularly if clients have to visit multiple vendors in person or make numerous phone calls to coordinate details. This can be particularly challenging for clients who work full-time or have other commitments.

1.2. Objectives of the study

1.2.1. General Objective

To develop a comprehensive and user-friendly Event planner Web-Based application that can simplify the event planning process for clients.

1.2.2. Specific Objective

This Study Aim to develop an application that:

To offer an inspiration gallery that features real event photos, ideas, and themes that clients can use for their own event, in order to help them create a personalized and memorable party experience.

2. To provide a budget tracker feature within the Web-Based application that allows clients to set a budget, track expenses, and receive alerts if they exceed their budget, in order to help them manage their finances more effectively.

3. To offer a checklist feature that provides a list of all the tasks that need to be completed for the events, such as selecting a venue, hiring vendors, and sending out invitations, in order to help clients stay organized and on track with their planning.

Scope

The Web-Based application will provide a comprehensive set of features and tools to help clients plan their events, including a budget tracker, vendor directory, checklist, guest list manager, and inspiration gallery. The budget tracker feature will allow couples to set a budget, track expenses, and receive alerts if they exceed their budget. The vendor directory feature will list various vendors, such as photographers, caterers, and florists, and allow couples to browse through the directory, read reviews, and contact vendors directly from the Web-Based application. The checklist feature will provide a list of all the tasks that need to be completed for the events, such as selecting a venue, hiring vendors, and sending out invitations. The guest list manager feature will allow clients to keep track of their guests' RSVPs, meal preferences, and seating arrangements. The inspiration gallery feature will feature real wedding photos, ideas, and themes that clients can use for their own events.

Delimitation

The Web-Based application will not provide any legal advice or assistance with obtaining marriage licenses or other legal requirements. The Web-Based application will not be responsible for any errors or inaccuracies in the information provided by vendors or third-party sources. The Web-Based application will not guarantee the availability or quality of any vendors or services listed in the vendor directory feature.

2. Methodology

2.1. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Input Process Output

This conceptual model demonstrates the flow of information and activities involved in the study of event planning and cost estimation, emphasizing the importance of translating client input into a well-structured budget and execution plan while maintaining financial control throughout the process. It serves as a simplified representation of the key elements in this field of study.

2.2. System architecture

Figure 2 System architecture diagram

The above figure 2.0 shows the System Architecture Diagram model of Event planning and Cost Estimation, it shows the diagram of the system in architectural design of the system.

The Event planning and Cost Estimation that provides a web-based front-end for Clients and Admin to interact with the system. It includes a user interface, a login page, application forms, a database for data storage, an online database, The system can be easily maintainable, and up gradable, ensuring it can adapt to the changing needs of the Event planning and Cost Estimation.

2.3. System development

Figure 3 Agile Methodology

The Figure 3.0 Agile methodology divides a project into many parts and uses those phases for managing the project. Continued enhancement in every stage and constant communication among all parties are required. Teams cycle through a process of planning, carrying out, and assessing once the job starts.

Agile methodology is a helpful project management approach because it enables the incorporation of changes in direction at the end of the process. The software development team benefits from this flexibility by being able to take into account ongoing stakeholder feedback.

2.4. Instrumental Used

The main tool for researchers used to collect data was a survey interview and the interview was carefully developed to contain a set of structured questions that were aimed for event planning and cost and due to this using an effective instrument, the researchers were able to collect insightful data from wide range of respondents, reflected on their viewpoints, experiences, and planning event and predicting too. The survey interview made it possible to acquire in-depth data, viewpoints, and viewpoints on the issues, methods, and ideal techniques related to planning event and cost estimation. In general, the survey interview was an effective strategy for acquiring important knowledge regarding event planning and cost estimation, strengthening the researchers' extending the breadth of understanding currently known in this field.

3. Result

In this section, the researchers delve into the outcomes of their comprehensive research and engage in a detailed analysis of the data and findings. The primary objective of this portion is to not only present the results but also to provide an in-depth interpretation. Data are collected from a total of fifty (50) respondents comprising Professionals and Parents. The selection of subjects is based on their affiliation to the Event Program.

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Types of Respondents	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Professionals	4	8%
Parents	46	92%
TOTAL	50	100%

Table 2 Verbal Interpretation

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Excellent
4	3.41 – 4.20	Very Good
3	2.61 – 3.40	Good
2	1.81 – 2.60	Fair
1	1.00 – 1.80	Poor

3.1. Evaluation Of Respondents according to ISO25010 criteria

Table 3 Respondents Evaluation According to Functionality

Functionality	5	4	3	2	1	W-M	V.I
1.How would you agree the completeness of features and functions in JuanKasalApp for event planning and cost estimation?	13	27	13	0	0	4.02	Very Good
2. Does JuanKasalApp allow for smooth interactions or integration with other systems or platforms that you use for event planning or related tasks	12	20	20	0	0	3.89	Very Good
3.In your experience with JuanKasalApp, how often did the application produce the expected results when performing tasks related to event planning and cost estimation	20	16	16	0	1	4.08	Very Good
Weighted Mean						3.99	Very Good

Table 4 Respondent Evaluation According to Performance

Performance	5	4	3	2	1	W-M	V.I
1. How would you rate the response time of JuanKasalApp when performing various tasks related to event planning and cost estimation?	17	23	13	0	0	4.10	Very Good
2.JuanKasalApp efficiently utilizes system resources and maintains a high level of quality during usage.	17	23	13	0	0	4.12	Very Good
Weighted Mean						4.11	Very Good

Table 5 Respondent Evaluation According to Usability

Usability	5	4	3	2	1	W-M	V.I
1. JuanKasalApp is easy to understand, and its user interface and navigation are straightforward.	17	19	17	0	0	4.06	Very Good
2. JuanKasalApp allows you to perform the desired outcomes and tasks related to event planning efficiently.	14	22	15	1	0	4.02	Very Good
3. JuanKasalApp is easy to learn and become proficient in?	21	16	14	1	0	4.16	Very Good
4.JuanKasalApp design is visually appealing, simple, and unique, making it stand out and attract attention.	19	19	14	0	0	4.12	Very Good
Weighted Mean						4.09	Very Good

Table 6 Respondent Evaluation According to Reliability

Reliability	5	4	3	2	1	W-M	V.I
1. I find JuanKasalApp to be mature, with most of the faults eliminated, and the system remains operative.	21	16	16	0	0	4.10	Very Good
2. JuanKasalApp is accessible when needed and available for the required use.	20	15	17	1	0	4.10	Very Good
3. JuanKasalApp demonstrates good fault tolerance and effectively handles errors.	15	22	15	1	0	3.95	Very Good
Weighted Mean						4.05	Very Good

Table 7 Respondent Evaluation According to Maintainability

Maintainability	5	4	3	2	1	W-M	V.I
1. JuanKasalApp demonstrates stability and makes it easy to change flaws in the system caused by incorrect inputs	15	18	19	0	0	3.93	Very Good
2. JuanKasalApp is highly modifiable, allowing for the easy modification of variables within the system	10	25	18	0	0	3.89	Very Good
3. JuanKasalApp supports Reusability, enabling the reuse of components for future use.	19	18	16	0	0	4.08	Very Good
Weighted Mean						3.97	Very Good

Table 8 Respondents Evaluation of Distributions to Respondents According to ISO25010 criteria

ISO25010	Weighted Mean	Verbal Implication
Functionality	3.99	Very Good
Performance	4.11	Very Good
Usability	4.09	Very Good
Reliability	4.05	Very Good
Maintainability	3.97	Very Good
General Weighted Mean	4.04	Very Good

3.2. Confusion matrix

- Scheme: weka.classifiers.Bayes.Naive Bayes Relation: Book4 Instances: 49 Attributes:
- 17
- ⚭id gender
- Completeness
- Correctness

- Appropriateness
- Time Behavior
- Resource
- Utilization
- Recognizability
- Operability
- Learnability
- Aesthetic
- Maturity
- Availability
- Fault Tolerance
- Stability
- Modifiability
- Reusability
- Test mode: 10-fold cross-validation
- === Classifier model (full training set) ===
- Naive Bayes Classifier
- Class
- Attribute Satisfied Very Good Good
- (0.37) (0.35) (0.29)

=====

ï»¿id

Mean 26.5 25.1765 22.8571

std. dev. 13.997 15.6289 11.9991

weight sum 18 17 14

Precision 1 1 1

- Correctly Classified Instances 34 69.3878 %
- Incorrectly Classified Instances 15 30.6122 %
- Kappa statistic 0.5418
- Mean absolute error 0.1821
- Root mean squared error 0.3964
- Relative absolute error 41.035 %
- Root relative squared error 83.9899 %
- Total Number of Instances 49

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

TP Rate FP Rate Precision Recall F-Measure MCC ROC Area PRC Area

Class

0.556 0.161 0.667 0.556 0.606 0.412 0.853 0.794 Satisfied

0.588 0.219 0.588 0.588 0.588 0.369 0.829 0.716 Very

Good

1.000 0.086 0.824 1.000 0.903 0.868 0.992 0.980 Good

Weighted Avg. 0.694 0.160 0.684 0.694 0.685 0.528 0.884 0.820

=== Confusion Matrix ===

a b c <-- classified as

10 7 1 | a = Satisfied

5 10 2 | b = Very Good

0 0 14 | c = Good

3.3. Summary Output

Table 9 Regression Statistics

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.36471907
R Square	0.13302
Adjusted R Square	-0.253383529
Standard Error	15.80804337
Observations	49

Table 10 ANOVA

	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	15	1303.596001	86.90640005	0.372613638	0.977474015
Residual	34	8496.403999	249.8942353		
Total	49	9800			

Table 11 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Table

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	7.943455098	16.93066723	0.469175549	0.641938947	-26.46380041	42.35071061	-26.46380041	42.35071061
Completeness	1.964827001	5.143501778	0.382001812	0.704837314	-8.488026246	12.41768025	-8.488026246	12.41768025
Correctness	2.136443546	4.286565379	0.498404517	0.621407982	-6.574905409	10.8477925	-6.574905409	10.8477925

Appropriateness	-2.685976839	3.951352379	-0.679761403	0.501257854	-10.71609102	5.344137338	-10.71609102	5.344137338
Time Behavior	0.301518296	5.032614756	0.059912851	0.952575826	-9.925985409	10.529022	-9.925985409	10.529022
Resource Utilization	0.034486868	5.393326707	0.006394359	0.994935447	-10.92607172	10.99504545	-10.92607172	10.99504545
Recognizability	0	0	65535	#NUM!	0	0	0	0
Operability	6.448171138	4.2132601	1.530446966	#NUM!	-2.114203565	15.01054584	-2.114203565	15.01054584
Learnability	-0.932950629	4.146457173	-0.224999461	0.823326549	-9.359565453	7.493664195	-9.359565453	7.493664195
Aesthetic	-3.804851252	4.305007666	-0.883819855	0.383000649	-12.55367944	4.94397694	-12.55367944	4.94397694
Maturity	8.163331696	7.06772872	1.15501486	0.256137543	-6.200021189	22.52668458	-6.200021189	22.52668458
Availability	-6.703300954	6.885615028	-0.973522471	0.337169375	-20.69655429	7.289952381	-20.69655429	7.289952381
Fault Tolerance	1.812496211	5.57802876	0.324934899	0.74722134	-9.52342211	13.14841453	-9.52342211	13.14841453
Stability	2.437399686	2.85470336	0.853818901	0.39918111	-3.364055542	8.238854915	-3.364055542	8.238854915
Modifiability	-3.705997532	5.570836836	-0.6652497	0.510378672	-15.0273001	7.61530504	-15.0273001	7.61530504
Reusability	-0.918255655	5.69574118	-0.161217939	0.872875927	-12.49339439	10.65688308	-12.49339439	10.65688308

The results of the coefficient table in multiple regression has the figures and charts presented. The coefficient of the term represents the change in the mean response for one unit of change in that term. If the coefficient is negative, as the term increases, the mean value of the response decreases. If the coefficient is positive, as the term increases, the mean value of the response increases. Functional Completeness, Correctness, Functional Appropriateness, Time Behavior, Resource Utilization, Recognizability, Operability, Learnability, Aesthetic, Maturity, Availability, Fault Tolerance, Stability, Modifiability and Reusability are parts of the data.

In conclusion of the data gathering, the study achieved a very good response from the respondents. It has been possible to improve learning and acquire specific subject-related skills. Specific event management applications provide numerous benefits to help with event planning and management. The methodology divides a project into many parts and uses those phases for managing the project. Continued enhancement in every stage and constant communication among all parties are required.

4. Discussion

The summary of the findings implies that the study would be very beneficial to clients planning for events. According to Drat ch-Parker, "a wedding planner is someone who plans the entire event." "A wedding coordinator focuses on the logistical planning and support of the wedding day. The couple has done all the main planning leading up to their wedding and only needs help with the final planning and execution of the event to keep things on track." As you pursue the responsibilities of planners below, keep in mind that full-service planners provide comprehensive coverage of the planning process, while month- or day-of coordinators usually only take care of last-minute logistics and details.

Creating a budget is one of the first stages of planning any event. Many couples may find this challenging because they are unaware of the true cost of a wedding. That's the role of a wedding planner, then. A planner can help couples maximize their budget by providing a reliable estimate of the cost of their desired event in their location, based on their extensive experience in the industry. "Perhaps the most important responsibility is working to develop a realistic budget that not only matches the expectations of the couple but also what they can truly afford," she says. "This part is crucial to having a positive outcome and provides the foundation for a successful wedding. Working together throughout the process to be sure the budget is always a consideration is the sign of a seasoned planner.

I would implicate to the system application or this study to create a plan of venue location that is nearby the house of the clients. For them to prevent costly transportation expenses. I would also suggest to develop the system where they would

scan the background of the caterers, location, make-up artist and hairstylist, flower arranger, a writing comments and feed-backs from the previous clients. To be able to know by the upcoming clients the legitimacy of the companies and people they are working with. If they had a bad record from the clients and has a good service.

4.1. User's manual

<p>Log in page</p> <p>Enter your email and password, And click "sign in" "a"</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● When you want to create another account <p>Please" click " the register account</p> <p>In account registration click register and click the name,email, password and confirm password and "Click" the "Sign up"</p>	<p>And when you finish logging in, you will see the</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Event choice here you can shop for events that can be reserved with us if you will be availing us. the next thing you will see is the ● List service Here like the event choice you can also see here the available services that we can offer you such as photographers, musicians, catering and etc. 	<p>Table of Contents (Planner)</p> <p>Log ipage_____1</p> <p>Register Account_____1</p> <p>Event Choice_____1</p> <p>List Service_____1</p> <p>Admin's Registration_____2</p> <p>User's Account_____2</p> <p>Service add,edit,and delete_____2</p> <p>Events add, insert and delete_____2</p>
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	<p>Log-in Page</p>	<p>User's Manual</p> <p><i>Planner</i></p> <p>Planner's Client</p> <p>Prepared by:</p> <p>Baldonado, Jericho Macabata, Mharjorie Frivaldo, Abegail</p>
<p>Account Registration</p>		
	<p>Events Choices</p>	
<p>List of Services</p>		

<p>Log in page</p> <p>Enter your email and password, And click “sign in”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● When you want to create another account <p>Please” click “ the register account In account registration click register and click the name,email, password and confirm password and “Click” the “Sign up”</p>	<p>And when you finish logging in, you will see the</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Event choice here you can shop for events that can be reserved with us if you will be availing us. the next thing you will see is the ● List service Here like the event choice you can also see here the available services that we can offer you such as photographers, musicians, catering and etc. 	<p>Table of Contents (Planner)</p> <p>Log ipage _____ 1</p> <p>Register Account _____ 1</p> <p>Event Choice _____ 1</p> <p>List Service _____ 1</p> <p>Admin Registration _____ 2</p> <p>User’s Account _____ 2</p> <p>Service add,edit,and delete _____ 2</p> <p>Events add, insert and delete _____ 2</p>
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5. Conclusion

Following the completion of data collection, the study received a very positive response from the respondents. It was possible to improve learning and acquire subject-specific skills. Specific event management applications offer numerous advantages for event planning and management. The methodology divides a project into many phases, which are then used to manage the project. Continuous improvement at each stage, as well as constant communication among all parties, are required. Once the job begins, teams go through a cycle of planning, carrying out, and evaluating. There are suggestions, but the project study will be sufficient to assist clients with event planning and provide satisfactory service. According to the findings summary, the study would be extremely beneficial to clients planning events. According to Dratch-Parker, "a wedding planner is someone who plans the entire event." "A wedding coordinator focuses on the logistical planning and support of the wedding day. The couple has done all of the main planning leading up to their wedding and only needs help with the final planning and execution of the event to keep things on track." Creating a budget is one of the first steps in event planning.

Creating a budget is one of the first steps in event planning. Many couples may struggle with this because they are unaware of the true cost of a wedding. That is, after all, the job of a wedding planner. A planner can assist couples in making the most of their budget by providing a reliable estimate of the cost of their desired event in their location, based on their extensive industry experience. "Perhaps the most important responsibility is working to develop a realistic budget that not only matches the expectations of the couple but also what they can truly afford," she said. "This part is critical to achieving a positive outcome and laying the groundwork for a successful wedding; working together throughout the process to ensure the success of the wedding."

I would involve the system application or this study in developing a venue location plan that is close to the clients' home. For them to avoid costly transportation costs. I would also propose that they create a system in which they scan the background of the caterers, location, make-up artist and hairstylist, flower arranger, and a writing comments and feedback from previous clients. To be able to determine the legitimacy of the companies and people with whom they are working from prospective clients. If they have a good service and a bad track record with clients.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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